

Be(II), Mg(II) and Ca(II) Complexes of Penicillins

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The chelating behaviour of penicillins has been studied with the metal ions, Be(II), Mg(II) and Ca(II) using Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique, at three temperatures 20°, 30° and 40° in 50% (V/V) acetone-water mixture and an ionic strength of 0.1 M with NaClO₄. The proton ligand and metal ligand formation constants have been calculated by various computational methods. The order of stability obtained :Be(II) > Mg(II) > Ca(II) follows order of $e^{\nu r}$, 11 nd ionisation potential, sum of 1st and 11nd ionisation potentials and electro-negativities of the metals.

METAL complexes play an important part in the biological activity of a drug, since chelation with metal ions has been suggested one of the important mechanism for drug action^{1,2}. Although chelating behaviour of many therapeutic drugs has been reported in the literature, no information is available on chelation of metal ions with the two most common and widely used penicillins, penicillin-G (PG) and penicillin-V (PV). In the present investigation, stepwise proton-ligand stability constants and metal-ligand stability constants of the two penicillins with a carcinogenic metal ion Be(II) and two biologically active metal ions, Mg(II) and Ca(II) have been calculated by various computational methods described by Irving-Rossotti³ using the Bjerrum-Calvin⁴ pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁵. Preliminary stoichiometric studies in solution were done using conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations employing the monovariation method⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals employed were of high purity. The solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardised by appropriate standard methods.

Conductometric studies were done on WTW, LBR, Germany conductivity bridge, while pH measurements were done on 'Systronics' pH meter, No 322, using glass calomel electrode assembly in conjunction with saturated calomel electrode.

Penicillin-G or -V solution was prepared in 80% acetone-water (v/v) mixture, by percolating a solution of sodium/potassium salt of the same through a column of Amberlite, IR-120, cation exchanger resin (H⁺-form) and washing the column with 80% acetone-water solvent. Penicillin (-G or -V) solutions thus obtained were then standardised with a standard alkali before use.

For potentiometric titrations, following mixtures, keeping the total volume 50 ml with 1 : 1 (V/V) acetone-water as solvent, were titrated against carbonate free 0.2 M KOH:

- (A) 5 ml 0.04 M HClO₄
- (B) Mixture (A) + 10 ml 0.02 M ligand solution
- (C) Mixture (B) + 5 ml 0.002 M metal solution

The ionic strength was kept 0.1 M in each case by adding appropriate quantities of 1.0 M NaClO₄. Titrations were carried out in a specially designed 100ml cell, which has an outer jacket for circulation of water at a fixed temperature from a thermostat with a water circulating device. The cell had a plastic lid with appropriate holes to accommodate the electrodes burette nozzle and nitrogen bubbling device.

pH-meter readings obtained at a given alkali addition in duplicate titrations were reproducible with the maximum variation of 0.025 pH unit. Correction of pH in 50% acetone-water system was done as described by Van-Uitert and Hass⁷ and Irving and Rossotti⁸. From the shifts in the pH titration curves values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated by Irving-Rossotti equations⁸. From \bar{n}_A values of the ligands at various pH values, proton-ligand stability constant, K^H , for PG and PV were obtained by (a) the half integral method (From the plot of \bar{n}_A vs pH), (b) point wise calculation, using the equation :

$$\log K_1^H = pH + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A}$$

and (c) the linear plot method (plotting $\log \bar{n}_A / 1 - \bar{n}_A$ vs pH). The result obtained are recorded in Table 1 and are found in agreement.

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TABLE 1—PROTON LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS

(a) Half integral method (b) Linear plot method
(c) Point wise calculation method.

Ligand	log K ₁ ^H			Method
	20°C	30°C	40°C	
PV	4.28	4.03	3.55	a
	4.28	4.03	3.50	b
	3.97	3.88	3.41	c
	(4.17)	(3.98)	(3.49)	
PG	5.00	4.93	4.45	a
	5.05	4.90	4.40	b
	4.82	4.50	4.28	c
	(4.88)	(4.77)	(4.37)	

The stepwise formation constants of the metal complexes were obtained by plotting formation curves, between the values of \bar{n} and pL. The values of log K₁ and log K₂ were directly read from their formation curves. The refined values were obtained by the best least square fit. The result obtained are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The values of proton-ligand formations constants, K₁^H, vary as : PG > PV (Table-1). This may be attributed to the difference in the electronegativity of the substituents in the side chains of the ligands. Presence of phenoxy-methyl group in PV, exerts greater electron with drawing effect than that of benzyl group in PG.

Preliminary conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations, using Nair and Pande's monovariation method⁶ indicate formation of ML and ML₂ complexes with penicillins and the metals used in this investigation. The maximum values of \bar{n}_A (≈ 2) also confirm the formation of two complexes, ML and ML₂.

Further, pH-titrations reveal that in all cases, only one proton is released during complexation of each molecule of any of the ligands. Thus the reactions may be represented as follows :

Where, M⁺⁺ = Be(II), Mg(II) or Ca(II) and
HL = PG or PV.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS

$\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄), (a) Half \bar{n} method
(b) Least Square method

Ligand	Temp.	Method	Be(II)				Mg(II)		Ca(II)		
			log K ₁	log K ₂	log β_2	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β_2	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β_2
PV	20°C	a	4.96	4.50	9.46	4.35	3.80	8.15	4.20	3.72	7.92
		b	(4.98)	(4.50)	(9.48)	(4.36)	(3.84)	(8.20)	(4.21)	(3.72)	(7.93)
	30°C	a	4.70	4.15	8.85	4.21	3.70	7.91	4.10	3.62	7.72
		b	(4.68)	(4.21)	(8.90)	(4.12)	(3.61)	(7.73)	(4.08)	(3.57)	(7.65)
	40°C	a	4.30	3.90	8.20	3.70	3.45	7.17	3.61	3.29	6.90
		b	(4.41)	(3.87)	(8.28)	(3.80)	(3.43)	(7.29)	(3.73)	(3.29)	(7.02)
PG	20°C	a	5.20	4.60	9.80	4.67	4.15	8.82	4.50	4.10	8.60
		b	(5.21)	(4.67)	(9.78)	(4.69)	(4.25)	(8.94)	(4.47)	(4.10)	(8.57)
	30°C	a	5.00	4.40	9.40	4.55	3.55	8.50	4.40	3.80	8.20
		b	(4.98)	(4.62)	(9.44)	(4.40)	(4.05)	(8.38)	(4.12)	(3.92)	(8.04)
	40°C	a	4.75	4.20	8.25	4.40	3.72	8.10	4.27	3.62	7.89
		b	(4.77)	(4.20)	(8.98)	(4.10)	(3.76)	(7.86)	(4.05)	(3.73)	(7.78)

With Be(II) and Mg(II) a precipitate was obtained on progressive addition of alkali during the titration. With PG at pH 5.7 and 4.5, while with PV at pH 5.6 and 5.5 respectively. This might be because of salt formation as experienced by Albert⁸ in other systems. In these cases all the calculations have been done below the pH of precipitations. Further, with the use of very dilute solutions ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$) of the metals, possibility of the formation of polynuclear complexes may be ruled out.

A perusal of Table 2 clearly indicates that the order of the stability constants of the metal complexes (with the two ligands) follows the order of basic strength of the ligands used in this investigation i.e. PG complexes are more stable than the PV complexes. While, the order obtained with the metals and any of the ligands follows the order of atomic number, e^2/r -ratio, electronegativities, second ionisation potentials and the sum of the first and second ionisation potentials of the metals :

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